
COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS OF PAKISTAN'S RENEWABLE ENERGY LANDSCAPE

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ABSTRACT

This research paper provides an in-depth analysis of Pakistan's renewable energy landscape till 2022, focusing on wind, hydro, solar, geothermal and biomass energy. It presents a comprehensive overview of the current state of renewable energy projects in Pakistan, including operational and under-construction wind, hydro and solar stations, as well as biomass energy plants. The paper also discusses ongoing projects and upcoming independent power producers (IPPs) in the renewable energy sector, highlighting the potential for further development and growth. Additionally, the paper examines the key organizations and institutions involved in policy-making and implementation of renewable energy resources in Pakistan. The research aims to contribute to the understanding of renewable energy policies and strategies in Pakistan, with a focus on sustainability and environmental protection.

Keywords Renewable Energy · Environmental Protection · Sustainability

1 Introduction

Pakistan has significant potential for renewable energy generation due to its abundant solar, wind, and hydropower resources. Solar power is the most accessible and affordable form of renewable energy in Pakistan, with a currently installed capacity totaling 2 GW. Wind power is also becoming increasingly popular in Pakistan, with an installed capacity of 1 GW. However, hydropower remains Pakistan's least developed form of renewable energy, with an installed capacity of only 100 MW.

Pakistan has many ways to make energy from the earth's natural resources. The country's diverse landscapes, including plains, deserts, mountains, and glaciers, make it a great place for various business projects. In the northern areas, projects of all sizes have been successful. The central region, with its high levels of sunlight, is ideal for building wind and solar power facilities. Both Sindh and Baluchistan have a lot of untapped potential for wind energy. Since Pakistan relies heavily on agriculture, it can generate power from its sugar cane industry (1).

2 Renewable Energy in Pakistan

Renewable energy in Pakistan has emerged as a critical component of the nation's energy strategy, aimed at addressing energy security, environmental sustainability, and economic development. The country boasts abundant renewable resources, including hydropower, solar, wind, bioenergy, and geothermal energy, which offer a diverse and sustainable energy mix. Following are the main sources of renewable energy in Pakistan.

2.1 Hydropower Energy

Hydropower, or water energy, is a cost-effective and useful way to generate energy, and Pakistan has actively utilized this source. The country has implemented numerous hydroelectric projects, resulting in a capacity of 7120 megawatts by June 2015. These hydro-dams not only provide energy but also store water for crops during droughts, benefiting many people in villages dependent on agriculture.

The Water and Power Development Authority (WAPDA) manages 6902 megawatts, while international power producers (IPPs) own 213 megawatts. Private investment is crucial for large hydropower projects like Suki Kinari Hydropower, Azad Pattan Hydropower, and Chakothi Hattian Hydropower. China has shown interest in Pakistan's water development, as illustrated by the Karot hydropower project in figure given below:

Figure 1: Karot Hydropower Project in Pakistan Under CPEC

A noteworthy aspect is the use of the Build, Own, Operate, and Transfer (BOOT) model for the Karot hydropower project, marking the first time in the Silk Road's 30-year history. The National Electric Power Regulatory Authority (NEPRA) sets tariffs for these projects, reflecting their development. Despite having vast hydropower potential, certain regions like Gilgit-Baltistan face challenges due to the lack of connectivity to the national distribution network and their remote locations.

The river system's geography enables significant hydropower production in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK) and Punjab. The KPK Energy Development Board is actively working on small dams capable of producing 272 megawatts. Policy guidance has been provided to the private sector for the construction of 28 hydroelectric projects with a total capacity of 122 megawatts. Since 2008, the Private Power and Infrastructure Board (PPIB) has concentrated on small-scale energy initiatives (2).

2.2 Solar Energy

The amount of sunlight, known as global irradiance, significantly influences the installation of solar photovoltaic systems. The regions with the highest radiation levels are the south and southwest. In Pakistan, the southwest region experiences the highest sun irradiation, while the north and northeast have lower levels. The Himalayas and Karakoram regions have the highest annual global horizontal irradiance on Earth, measuring 2300 kWh/m². This value decreases as one moves northeast, but the region still receives a substantial amount of sunlight (3).

Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI) is a standard for solar photovoltaic cells, and it is widespread in Pakistan except for the Himalayas. Western Baluchistan, for example, has 2700 kWh/m²/year, with 80% of the land capable of producing 2000 kWh/m²/year. Comparing these values to sub-Saharan regions, particularly the Sinai Peninsula, shows favorable results.

Using PV-Sol Software, DNI values were determined for four provinces in Pakistan. Cities like Karachi and Hyderabad in Sindh have a DNI of 1834.5 kWh/m²/year. Sukkur and Jacobabad report DNIs of 1931.5 and 1934.7 kWh/m²/year. In Punjab, cities like Multan, Bahawalpur, Faisalabad, Sialkot, and Lahore have DNIs ranging from 1639.9 to 1998.3 kWh/m²/year. For Quetta, Zhob, and Qila-Saifullah, DNIs were measured at 2039.6, 2040.9, and 2014.8 kWh/m²/year, respectively.

The Alternative Energy Development Board (AEDB) has authorized and is developing solar power installations in various locations. A total of 22 solar PV projects with a capacity of 890.80 megawatts have been initiated by the AEDB. Additionally, six solar power facilities, totaling 430 megawatts, have been operational for five years (2).

Figure 2: Solar Radiation Map-Pakistan

2.3 Wind Energy

Wind energy plays a crucial role as a primary renewable source, and the process of wind mapping involves collaboration between international and local organizations. In Pakistan, the Pakistan Meteorological Department (PMD) and the National Renewable Energy Laboratories are responsible for mapping wind patterns. The figure 3 shows the wind map of Pakistan (4).

The Republican Party has highlighted the significance of southern Pakistan's Gharo Ketti Bandar wind corridors, projecting a potential of 50 GW. Various publications provide detailed information on wind resources and economic assessments. Gharo's wind resource and energy economics have been studied at different heights (10, 30, and 50 meters), confirming the site's suitability for utility wind turbines. Similarly, wind resource analyses for Karachi Port Trust and Sujawal, as well as wind potential assessments for Sanghar and Quaid Abad, demonstrate the viability of these locations for wind energy generation.

Gharo-Ketti Bandar is estimated to have the capacity to generate 1000 megawatts. The Alternative Energy Development Board (AEDB) reports success in wind energy initiatives, aligning with the government's goal to reduce dependence on more expensive energy sources. In Sindh, 23 Letters of Intent (LOIs) have been issued for wind energy projects, while the Punjab administration has shown readiness by aiming for wind installations with a capacity to generate 1710 megawatts. These efforts underline the commitment to harnessing wind energy as a sustainable and cost-effective power source in Pakistan (2).

2.4 Bioenergy

Recognizing the importance of bioenergy as a valuable resource, bioenergy mapping in Pakistan was completed in 2016. This mapping involves two key components. Firstly, satellite imagery, combined with field surveys, is used to categorize the land, enabling the evaluation of biomass energy potential in each area. The second part involves analyzing the technical potential based on survey results, identifying patterns of yield utilization.

In the United States, significant biomass sources are found in the industrial and agricultural sectors. Various crop husks, including rice and maize husks, serve as biomass sources in industrial settings. Additionally, agricultural biomass sources such as rice straw and wheat straw play a crucial role. By the end of December 2016, four sugar mills had completed the construction of facilities to generate energy from bagasse, resulting in a total installed capacity of 45 megawatts in a single bagasse plant. Ongoing developments in bagasse power stations aim to achieve a capacity of 217 megawatts.

Figure 3: Wind map of Pakistan

Figure 4 indicates that several companies have received letters of intent to produce biomass energy over the last five years. This suggests a growing interest and commitment to utilizing biomass as an energy source in Pakistan. Overall, the assessment and utilization of bioenergy resources contribute to a more diversified and sustainable energy portfolio for the country (2).

Figure 4: Under the ECC-approved policy, a letter of intent to produce biomass energy was handed to the following companies

2.5 Geothermal Energy

As of now, the vast majority of Pakistan's geothermal energy potential remains untapped. There is currently no systematic approach in place for evaluating the possibilities of geothermal energy exploration. However, several studies suggest that geothermal energy can be harnessed across all provinces of Pakistan.

In the Makran region, offshore mud volcanoes are rare in the shallow shelf area, but the mud active zone (MAZ) encompasses the mud volcanoes found in this region. Satellite images of these mud volcanoes reveal distinct flow patterns and flux, providing observable evidence of geothermal activity. The Geological Survey of Pakistan identifies principal hotspots for geothermal activity in the Himalayan collision zone, the Indus basin, and the Chaghi area of Baluchistan. Researchers have found indications of geothermal energy in areas also prone to seismic activity. The findings of quantification efforts are then applied to estimate the probability of geothermal resource exploitation (5).

Figure 5: Geothermal resource potential of Pakistan

Despite this potential, a comprehensive assessment of geothermal energy is needed, and the most suitable areas for exploitation must be determined. Therefore, further evaluations are required, and the results need to be incorporated to make informed decisions. Geothermal energy, as an alternative source, is often considered a feasible option, and ongoing efforts in assessment and exploration will contribute to its potential utilization in Pakistan.

3 Potential of Renewable Energy Sources in Pakistan

Renewable energy in Pakistan is a relatively underdeveloped sector, however, in recent years, there has been more and more interest to explore renewable energy resources for the energy production. Around 10.57% of Pakistan's total installed power generation capacity (in 2020) comes renewables (wind, solar and biogas). Most of Pakistan's renewable energy comes from hydroelectricity. As per the vision of the Prime Minister, there is the aim to induct 20% of RE by the year 2025 and 30% of renewable energy by the year 2030.

The amount of wind power generated has increased significantly over the past ten years, ranking as the second-highest renewable energy source in terms of electricity generation in the global. The Alternative Energy Development Board (AEDB) of the Government of Pakistan states that, as indicated in Table 1, the estimated gross potential of wind power in the Gharo-Keti Bandar Wind Corridor in the coastal area of Sindh province is approximately 42,000 MW. Currently, the wind power capacity is only 106 MW (6).

Approximations from the DOE's 2006 "Solar Energy Utilization" report the sun is so strong that it could supply over 10,000 times the energy required by the entire planet if we could capture all of its energy! Check out our sites on solar

Table 1: Potential of Renewable Energy in Pakistan

Source	Potential
Wind Energy	42,000 MW
Solar Energy	535,000 GWh
Hydro-power Energy	41,700 MW

technology to learn how researchers are attempting to harness as much energy as they can. Other renewable energy sources must be used in addition to solar energy because it is impractical to expect to be able to capture all that energy at the precise moment, we need it (7).

Figure 6: Maximum Possible Potential of Renewable Energy Resources

4 Pakistan's Energy Landscape

Pakistan's dependence on non-renewable energy sources comes with environmental and economic challenges. As the country strives for a more sustainable future, renewable energy options like hydro-power, wind, and solar power offer a promising path forward. The below table presents the current installed capacity (as of July 2023) of these emerging sources, indicating their potential to reshape Pakistan's energy landscape.

Pakistan has a total installed power generation capacity of 43,775 MW as of 30 June 2022 which includes 26,683 MW thermal, 10,635 MW hydroelectric, 1,838 MW wind, 630 MW solar, 369 MW bagasse and 3,620 MW nuclear (8).

Table 2: Renewable and Non-Renewable Energy Resources in Pakistan

Renewable Energy Resources		Non Renewable Energy Resources	
Energy	Installed Capacity (MW)	Energy	Installed Capacity (MW)
Hydro-power	10,635	Thermal (Fossil Fuels)	26,683
Wind	1,838	Nuclear	3620
Solar	630		
Biomass	369		
Total Renewable Energy	13,472	Total Non Renewable Energy	30,303

5 Installed System of Renewable Energy in Pakistan

According to National Electric Power Regulatory Authority's (NEPRA) 2022 yearly report, Pakistan's total installed power generation capacity is 43,775 MW, of which 59% of energy comes from thermal (fossil fuels), 25% from hydro, 7% from renewable (wind, solar and biomass), and 9% from nuclear.

5.1 Hydroelectric Power Stations

Energy from water is considered renewable energy because it uses the Earth's water cycle and gravitational pull to generate electricity. It also does not emit greenhouse gas emissions or air pollutants.

5.1.1 In-service Hydropower Stations

Here is a list of in-service hydropower stations in Pakistan as per NEPRA Report 2022 (8).

Table 3: In service hydropower stations in Pakistan as per NEPRA Report 2022

Station	Location	Type of Power Station	Capacity (MW)	In-Service year
Renala	Renala, Punjab	Run of Canal	1	1925
Malakand	Malakand, KPK	Run of River	22	1935
Rasul	Mandi Bahauddin, Punjab	Run of Canal	22	1952
Dargai	Malakand, KPK	Run of Canal	20	1952
Kurram Garhi	Kurram Garhi, KPK	Run of Canal	4	1958
Chichonki Malian	Sheikhupura, Punjab	Run of Canal	13	1959
Warsak	Peshawar, KPK	Run of River	243	1960
Shadiwal	Shadiwal, Punjab	Run of Canal	14	1961
Nandipur	Gujranwala, Punjab	Run of Canal	14	1963
Mangla	Mirpur, Azad Kashmir	Reservoir	1,000	1967
Chitral	Chitral, KPK	Run of Canal	1	1975
Tarbela	Tarbela, KPK	Reservoir	4,888	1977
Chashma	Chashma, Punjab	Run of River	184	2000
Jagran	Neelum, Azad Kashmir	Hydro	30	2000
Ghazi-Barotha	Attock, Punjab	Run of River	1,450	2003
Malakand-III	Malakand, KPK	Run of River Canal	84	2008
Khan Khwar	Shangla, KPK	Reservoir	72	2010
Pehur	Swabi, KPK	Canal Fall Run of River	18	2010
Jinnah	Jinnah Barrage, Punjab	Run of River	96	2012
Garam Chashma	Chitral, KPK	Hydro	1	2012
Allai Khwar	Mansehra, KPK	Reservoir	121	2013
Gomal Zam	South Waziristan	Reservoir	17	2013
New Bong Escape (Laraib Energy)	Mirpur, Azad Kashmir	Hydro	84	2013
Duber Khwar	Kohistan, KPK	Reservoir	130	2014
Patrind Hydro	Muzaffarabad, Azad Kashmir	Run of River	147	2017
Golen Gol	Chitral, KPK	Run of River	108	2018
Neelum-Jhelum	Muzaffarabad, Azad Kashmir	Run of River	969	2018
Marala Hydro (PPDCL)	Sialkot, Punjab	Canal Fall Run of River	8	2018
Gulpur Hydropower Plant, Barali	Kotli, Azad Kashmir	Run of River	100	2020

Table 3 continued from previous page

Daral Khwar	Swat District, KPK	Run of River	37	2021
Ranolia	Kohistan, KPK	High Head	17	2021
Karot	Azad Kashmir	Run of River	720	2022
Total In-Service Generation			10,635	

5.1.2 Under Construction Hydropower Stations

Here is a list of under construction hydropower stations in Pakistan as per NEPRA Report 2022 (8).

Table 4: Under Construction hydropower stations in Pakistan as per NEPRA Report 2022

Station	Community	Location	Capacity (MW)	Status
Kohala Hydropower Project	Muzaffarabad, Azad Kashmir	-	1124	Under construction. To be operational by 2025.
Azad Pattan Hydropower Project	Sudhanoti, Azad Kashmir	-	700	Under construction. To be operational by 2025.
Shingo Kas Hydropower Project	Dir, KPK	-	102	Under construction. To be operational by Mar 2024.
Nai Gaj Dam	Dadu, Sindh	-	4.2	Under construction. To be operational by Oct 2024.
Dasu Dam	Dasu, KPK	-	4,320	Under construction. Stage-I: 2,160 MW To be operational by April 2026.
Mohmand Dam	Mohmand Agency, KPK	34°21'11"N 71°31'58"E	800	Under construction. To be operational by Dec 2025.
Keyal Khwar Hydropower Project	Kohistan, KPK	Keyal Khwar River	128	Under construction. To be operational by 2026.
Tarbela Dam Extension-V	Tarbela, KPK	34°05'23"N 72°41'54"E	1,530	Under construction. To be operational by 2025.
Tangir Hydropower Project	Chilas, Gilgit Baltistan	-	218	Under construction. To be operational by 2028
Diamer-Bhasha Dam	Chilas, Gilgit Baltistan	-	4,500	Under construction. To be operational by Jun 2029.
Shingo Kas Hydropower Project	Dir, KPK	-	102	Under construction. To be operational by Mar 2024.
Total Under-Construction Generation			14,600+	

5.1.3 Proposed Hydropower Station

Here is a list of proposed hydropower stations in Pakistan as per NEPRA Report 2022 (8).

Table 5: Proposed hydropower stations in Pakistan as per NEPRA Report 2022

Station	Community	Capacity (MW)	Status
Balakot Hydropower Project	Mansehra, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa	300	Ready to be constructed in 2020.
Athmuqam Dam	Athmuqam, Azad Kashmir	350	Ready to be constructed. Korea Hydro & Nuclear Power Corporation won the contract for construction.

Table 5 continued from previous page

Toren More Project	KPK	35	Ready to be constructed. Sinohydro Corporation China and Sichuan Energy Industry Investment Group Co. Ltd. China won the contract for construction.
Turtonus-Uzghor Dam	Chitral, KPK	58	Ready to be constructed. Sinohydro Corp Ltd and Sachal Engineering Works Private Ltd won the contract for construction.
Lower Spat Gah hydropower project	Kohistan, KPK	496	Ready to be constructed.
Arkari Gol Hydropower Project	Chitral, KPK	99	Ready to be constructed.
Taunsa Barrage Hydropower Plant	Muzaffargarh, Punjab	120	Ready to be constructed.
Chianwali Hydropower Project	Gujranwala, Punjab	5.38	Ready to be constructed.
Deg Outfall Hydropower Project	Gujranwala, Punjab	4.04	Ready to be constructed.
Okara Hydropower Project	Gujranwala, Punjab	4.16	Ready to be constructed.
Chashma Hydrel Power Project	Mianwali, Punjab	5.0	Ready to be constructed.
Mahl Hydropower Project	Azad Kashmir	590	Ready to be constructed. China Three Gorges Corporation won the contract for construction.
Nekherdim-Paur Dam	Chitral, KPK	80	Ready to be constructed. CTG won the contract for construction.
Chakothei-Hattian Hydropower Project	Muzaffarabad, Azad Kashmir	500	Ready to be constructed. Chinese firm won the contract for construction.
Hanzel Hydropower Project	Hanzel, Gilgit	20	Ready to be constructed. Cost estimate \$63 million.
Kalam Asrit	Kalam, KPK	197	Ready to be constructed. KPK government signed MOU with Korea's state-owned M/S Korea South East Power Company. Cost estimate \$500 million.
Ghowari Hydropower Project	Gilgit-Baltistan	30	Ready to be constructed. Cost estimate \$80 million.
Bara Dam	Tirah, Khyber Agency	5.8	Ready to be constructed.
Bunji Hydropower Project	Astore District, Gilgit-Baltistan	7,100	Ready to be constructed. MOU signed with China's National Energy Administration. Cost estimate \$6.8 billion.
Kalabagh Dam	Mianwali District, Punjab	3600	Proposed.
Patan hydropower Project	Patan Village, Indus River	2,400	Ready to be constructed. MOU signed with China's National Energy Administration. Cost estimate \$6 billion.
Harpo Hydropower Project	Skardu, Gilgit Baltistan	34.5	Ready to be constructed.
Thakot Hydropower Project	Battagram District, KPK	4,000	Feasibility studies to be completed by Dec 2017. MOU signed with China's National Energy Administration. Cost estimate \$6 billion.
Phandar Hydropower Project	Gupis-Yasin GilgitBaltistan	81	Detailed engineering design or tender of documents under process. Cost estimate \$128 million .

Table 5 continued from previous page

Basho Hydropower Station	Skardu, GB, Indus River	28	Detailed engineering design or tender of documents under process. Cost estimate \$40 million.
Tank Zam Dam	Hinis Tangi, KPK, Tank Zam River	25.5	Feasibility studies completed. Cost estimate \$234 million.
Hingol Dam	Lasbela District, Hingol River, Balochistan	3.5	Feasibility studies completed. Cost estimate \$311 million.
Akhori Dam	Akhori, Punjab, Haro River	600	Feasibility studies ongoing. Cost estimate \$1.6 billion.
Katzarah Dam	Skardu, GilgitBaltistan	15000	Proposed.
Middle Palas hydropower project	Kohistan, KPK	373	Feasibility studies ongoing. Cost estimate \$763 million.
Upper Palas hydropower project	Kohistan, KPK	160	Feasibility studies ongoing. Cost estimate \$763 million.
Madian Hydropower Project	Swat, KPK, Swat River	157	Feasibility studies ongoing.
Shushai-Zhendoli Hydropower Project	Chitral, KPK	144	Financing is being arranged for these projects by selling shares in the existing projects.
Shogosin Hydropower Project	Chitral, KPK	132	Financing is being arranged for these projects by selling shares in the existing projects.
Latambar Dam	Karak District, Khyber Pukhtunkhwa Nowshera	-	The preliminary feasibility study of the project has been completed and process of site selection completed.
Mairoobi Dam	District, Khyber Pukhtunkhwa Nowshera	-	The preliminary feasibility study of the project has been completed and process of site selection completed.
Jaroba Dam	District, Khyber Pukhtunkhwa Mansehra	-	The preliminary feasibility study of the project has been completed and process of site selection completed.
Naran Dam	District, Khyber Pukhtunkhwa	188	EOI invited.
Gorband Hydropower Project	Shangla District, KPK	14	The preliminary feasibility study of the project has been completed and process of site selection completed.
Nand Bahar Dam	Battagram District, Khyber Pukhtunkhwa	50	The preliminary feasibility study of the project has been completed and process of site selection completed.
Mojigram Shagoor Dam	Chitral District, Khyber Pukhtunkhwa	50	The preliminary feasibility study of the project has been completed and process of site selection completed.
Astar Rabooni Dam	Chitral District, Khyber Pukhtunkhwa	50	The preliminary feasibility study of the project has been completed and process of site selection completed.
Arkari Gol Dam	Chitral District, Khyber Pukhtunkhwa	50	The preliminary feasibility study of the project has been completed and process of site selection completed.
Shringal Dam	Upper Dir District, Khyber Pukhtunkhwa	50	The preliminary feasibility study of the project has been completed and process of site selection completed.
Patrak Barikot Dam	Swat District, Khyber Pukhtunkhwa	60	The preliminary feasibility study of the project has been completed and process of site selection completed.

Table 5 continued from previous page

Segokatch Dam	Chitral District, KPK	60	The preliminary feasibility study of the project has been completed and process of site selection completed.
Taunsa Hydropower Project	-	135	IPP, RFP has been accepted.
Shigo Kas Hydropower Project	-	102	EOI invited.
Bata Kundi Hydropower Project	-	96	EOI invited.
Ghorband Khwar Hydropower Project	-	21	EOI invited.
Nandihar Khwar Hydropower Project	-	12	EOI invited.
Winder Dam	Lasbela District, Winder River, Balochistan	0.3	Proposed. Cost estimate \$148 million.
Daraban Zam Dam	Dera Ismail Khan, KPK, Khora River	0.75	Proposed. Cost estimate \$69 million.
Ghabir Dam	Ghabir River	0.15	Proposed. Cost estimate \$121 million
Papin Dam	Rawalpindi District, Wadala Kas	0.3	Proposed. Cost estimate \$101 million
Rajhdani Dam	Kotli District, AJK Poonch River	132	EOI invited
Gabral Kalam	Kalam, KPK	101	LoS issued.
Bhadi Dhoba Hydropower Project	Haveli District	1	Proposed.
Galeter Hydropower Project	Kotli District	1	Proposed.
Saridoa Cross Hydropower Project	Bhimber District	1.7	Proposed.
Chamfall Hydropower Project	Hattian District	6.4	Proposed.
Guddu Hydropower Station	Kashmore, Sindh	33	Proposed.
Harighel Hydropower Project	-	53	Proposed.
Sehra Hydropower Project	Azad Kashmir, Poonch River	130	Proposed.
Nagdar Hydropower Project	Neelum, AJK, Jagran River	25	Proposed.
Duvarian Hydropower Project	Hattian Bala, AJK, Jagran River	29	Proposed.
Asrit-Kedam Hydropower Project	Kalam, KPK, Swat River	215	LOI issued by PEDO
Karang Hydropower Project	-	458	Proposed.
Shogo-Sin Hydel Dam	-	132	Proposed.
Shushgai Zhendoll	-	144	Proposed.
Yogo, Pakistan	-	500	Proposed.
Thor Hydropower Project	-	3.6	Proposed.
Yulbo Hydropower Project	-	3000	Proposed.

Table 5 continued from previous page

Shyok Hydropower Project	-	520	Proposed.
Tungus Hydropower Project	-	2200	Proposed.
Skardu Dam	Skardu	1600	Proposed.
Dudhnial Hydropower Project	-	960	Proposed.
Kundal Shahi Hydropower Project	-	960	Proposed.
Trappi Hydropower Project	-	32	Proposed.
Nandihar Hydropower Project	Battagram, Khyber Pukhtunkhwa	10	Proposed.
Mujigaram Shagore Hydropower Project	Chitral, Khyber Pukhtunkhwa	51	Proposed.
Istaro Booni Hydropower Project	Chitral, Khyber Pukhtunkhwa	52	Proposed
Arkari Gol Hydropower Project	Chitral, Khyber Pukhtunkhwa	79	Proposed
Total Proposed Generation		30,237+	

5.2 Wind Energy Plants

AnchorPakistan has considerable potential for using wind energy in the coastal belt of Sindh and Baluchistan (in southern Pakistan). The GoP has developed a wind power energy corridor along the southern coastal regions of Sindh and Baluchistan. Wind data, provided by Pakistan's Meteorological Department, measures Pakistan's coastal belt at 60km (Gharo-Keti Bandar) and 180km long, with an exploitable potential of 50,000MW of electricity generation through wind turbines.

Currently, 36 private wind projects are operating, producing approximately 1845MW. The Government of Pakistan renewable energy (RE) policy envisages generating 60 percent of the country's energy from renewable resources by 2030. The ambitious target provides several opportunities for the wind energy market in Pakistan.

Here is the list of current Wind Energy Plants in Pakistan as per NEPRA Report 2022 (8). All of them located in Thatta, Sindh, Pakistan.

Table 6: Current Wind Energy Plants in Pakistan as per NEPRA Report 2022

Station	Company	Capacity
UEP 1	United Energy Pakistan Pvt. Ltd	66 MW
Metro Wind Power	Metro Wind Power (Pvt.) Limited	60 MW
Zorlu Enerji Pakistan	Zorlu Enerji Pakistan (Pvt.) Ltd	56 MW
ACT2 Wind	ACT2 Wind (Pvt.) Limited	50 MW
Artistic Wind Power	Artistic Wind Power (Pvt.) Limited	50 MW
Din Energy	Din Energy Limited	50 MW
Foundation Wind Energy 1	Fauji Foundation Wind Energy-I Limited	50 MW
Foundation Wind Energy 2	Fauji Foundation Wind Energy-II Limited	50 MW
Gul Ahmed Electric	Gul Ahmed Electric Limited	50 MW
Gul Ahmed Wind Power Ltd	Gul Ahmed Electric Limited	50 MW
Lakeside Energy	Lakeside Energy (Pvt.) Limited	50 MW
Liberty Wind Power 1	Liberty Wind Power 1 (Pvt.) Limited	50 MW
Liberty Wind Power 2	Liberty Wind Power 2 (Pvt.) Limited	50 MW
Lucky Star Yunus	Yunus Energy Limited	50 MW
Master Green Energy	Master Green Energy Limited	50 MW
Metro Power Plant	Metro Power Company Limited	50 MW

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Nasda Green Energy	Nasda Green Energy (Private) Limited	50 MW
Tricom Wind Power	Tricom Wind Power (Private) Limited	50 MW
Zephyr Power	Zephyr Power (Pvt.) Ltd	49.74 MW
Hawa Energy	Hawa Energy (Pvt.) Limited	49.74 MW
Jhampir Power	Jhampir Power (Pvt.) Limited	49.74 MW
Tricon Boston A	Tricon Boston Consulting Corporation (Pvt.) Ltd, Project-A	49.74 MW
Tricon Boston B	Tricon Boston Consulting Corporation (Pvt.) Ltd, Project-B	49.74 MW
Tricon Boston C	Tricon Boston Consulting Corporation (Pvt.) Ltd, Project-C	49.74 MW
FFC Energy	Fauji Fertilizer Company Energy Limited	49.50 MW
Hydro China Dawood Power	Hydro China Dawood Power	49.50 MW
Master Wind Energy	Master Wind Energy (Pvt.) Ltd	49.50 MW
Sachal	Sachal Energy Development Pvt. Ltd.	49.50 MW
Tenaga Generasi Limited	Tenaga Generasi Limited	49.50 MW
Three Gorges First Wind Farm	Three Gorges First Wind Farm Pakistan (Private) Limited	49.50 MW
Three Gorges Second Wind Farm	Three Gorges 2nd Wind Firm Pakistan (Pvt.) Limited	49.50 MW
Three Gorges Third Wind Farm	Three Gorges Third Wind Firm Pakistan (Pvt.) Limited	49.50 MW
Hartford Alternative Energy	Hartford Alternative Energy (Pvt.) Limited	49.30 MW
Indus Wind Energy	Indus Wind Energy Limited	50 MW
UEP 2	United Energy Pakistan Pvt. Ltd	33.00 MW
Tapal Wind Energy	Tapal Wind Energy (Pvt.) Limited	30.00 MW
Total Generation		1842 MW

5.3 Solar Stations

Pakistan has an average of nine and a half hours of sunlight daily. Solar power entered Pakistan's energy mix in 2013 after the government introduced a set of support policies to foster renewable energy development. According to the Private Power & Infrastructure Board (PPIB) of the Ministry of Energy, seven solar projects of 530 MW are operational and supplying electricity to the national grid.

With the rising costs of electricity in Pakistan and an unreliable grid supply, more industries and commercial organizations are turning to captive solar solutions. There has been a strong surge in domestic installation of rooftop photovoltaic panels in larger cities. For projects under 1 MW, net metering regulations came into effect in September 2015. The current state of the energy sector is promising for growth in solar power in the future, given rising fossil fuel prices. Here is the list known Solar in Pakistan as per NEPRA Report 2022 (8).

Table 7: Inservice Solar Station in Pakistan as per NEPRA Report 2022

Station	Location	Capacity (MW)	In-Service Year
Quaid-e-Azam Solar Park	Bahawalpur, Punjab	100	2015
Appolo Solar Development	Bahawalpur, Punjab	100	2016
Best Green Energy	Bahawalpur, Punjab	100	2016
Crest Energy	Bahawalpur, Punjab	100	2016
AJ Power Pvt. Ltd.	Khushab, Punjab	12	2017
Harappa Solar Pvt. Ltd	Sahiwal, Punjab	18	2017
Oursun Pakistan	Thatta, Sindh	50	2019
Gharo Solar	Thatta, Sindh	50	2020
Zhenfa Pakistan New Energy	Layyah, Punjab	100	2022

5.3.1 Under Construction Solar Stations

Here is the list known under construction solar stations in Pakistan as per NEPRA Report 2022 (8).

Table 8: Under Construction Solar Station in Pakistan as per NEPRA Report 2022

Station	Location	Capacity	Status
Meridian Energy (Pvt.) Ltd	Sukkur, Sindh	50 MW	Under Construction. Expected COD Feb 2023.
HNDS Energy (Pvt.) Limited	Sukkur, Sindh	50 MW	Under Construction. Expected COD Feb 2023.
Helios Power (Pvt.) Limited	Sukkur, Sindh	50 MW	Under Construction. Expected COD Feb 2023.

5.4 Biomass Energy Plants

Pakistan has massive potential for biomass energy, but its use is limited. While large plants like Sanawan exist, challenges like infrastructure and logistics hold back wider adoption. However, small-scale biogas plants are gaining traction in rural areas. The government aims to boost renewables, including biomass, by 2030. Overcoming challenges is key to unlocking clean energy potential for Pakistan. Here is the list of Inservice Biomass Energy Plants in Pakistan as per NEPRA Report 2022 (8).

Table 9: Inservice Biomass Energy Plants in Pakistan as per NEPRA Report 2022

Station	Location	Capacity	In-Service Date
Jamal Din Wali-II	Rahim Yar Khan, Punjab	26 MW	12 Jun, 2014
Jamal Din Wali-III	Rahim Yar Khan, Punjab	27 MW	3 Oct, 2014
RYK Mills	Rahim Yar Khan, Punjab	40 MW	24 Mar, 2015
Chiniot Power	Chiniot, Punjab	63 MW	28 Nov, 2015
Fatima Energy	Muzaffargarh, Punjab	120 MW	-
Hamza Sugar Mills	Rahim Yar Khan, Punjab	15 MW	Mar, 2017
The Thal Industries Corporation	Layyah, Punjab	20 MW	-
Almoiz Industries	Mianwali, Punjab	36 MW	Feb, 2019
Chanar Energy	Faisalabad, Punjab	22 MW	Feb, 2019

In addition to wind, solar, and biomass, Pakistan has diverse renewable energy resources waiting to be tapped, although most are still in their initial stages of development or research. Here's a brief overview of some others:

Hydropower is currently the country's main renewable energy source, accounting for about 25% of the total installed capacity and 10% of total generation. Pakistan has significant potential for further development of hydropower thanks to its mountainous terrain and large river systems.

Geothermal, studies suggest Pakistan has abundant geothermal resources, particularly in the north and west. However, harnessing this potential through geothermal power plants is yet to take off at a large scale.

Tidal, the coastline of Pakistan offers potential for tidal energy generation, especially near the Indus River delta. However, this technology is still in its early stages of development globally and hasn't been implemented commercially in Pakistan yet.

Micro-hydro, small-scale hydropower plants can be a valuable renewable energy source for remote areas. Although some exist, expanding their use could provide clean energy to underserved communities.

So, while only three renewable resources are currently generating significant amounts of energy in Pakistan, the country has a much wider range of potential sources waiting to be developed.

6 Ongoing Projects and Upcoming IPP's

Pakistan is considered the country with a positive forward thinking-nation working out for renewable energy's sustainability, technological development, and innovation. Pakistan has signed a pact with the UK-listed Oracle Power Public Ltd, to develop the country's first-ever green hydrogen energy plant in Sindh. Also, China plans to sign a 3-year-long pact to establish regional green energy projects. Scaling up green hydrogen will help Pakistan's economy to achieve net zero emissions and limit temperature rises. Thus, it is the most effective way to save the earth and energy.

6.1 Solar Power Projects in Pakistan

Pakistan is potentially enough to generate solar power; according to the World Bank, only 0.071% of the country's area is required for solar photovoltaic power generation – to meet the country's current demand.

Talking about sunlight exposure, Pakistan has an average of nine and a half hours of daily sunlight. Since 2013, the country is producing solar energy, and several industries, commercial organizations, and even government buildings and different upcoming real estate projects are also planning to go solar, aiming to support the economy in managing power distribution. Several solar power energy projects are in the pipeline, some of them are given below (9).

Table 10: Ongoing Solar Energy Projects

Location	Capacity	Projects	Status
Nooriabad, Sindh	50 MW	3	Awaiting
Dadu, Sindh	20 MW	3	Awaiting
Sultanabad, Rahim Yar Khan, Punjab	12 MW	1	Awaiting
Mehmood Kot, District Muzaffargarh, Punjab	50 MW	1	Awaiting
Noorsar, Bahawalnagar, Punjab	50 MW	1	Under-developed
Gharo, Thatta, Sindh	50 MW	2	Under-developed
Noorsar, Bahawalnagar, Punjab	30 MW	1	Under-developed

6.2 Wind Energy Projects in Pakistan

Wind energy is considered the most significant and sustainable for the survival of the growing population. Currently, wind energy is contributing 4% to Pakistan's electricity requirements. Well, the country has the potential to produce up to 340 GW of Electricity just from the wind, but if only planned strategically and utilized efficiently.

Another important yet favorable prospect of wind energy is the installation of wind turbines, which are economical, take up less space, and are easy-to-install, in windy areas. Some upcoming wind energy projects in Pakistan are given below (9).

Table 11: Ongoing Wind Energy Projects

Location	Capacity	Projects	Status
Gharo, Sindh	50 MW	1	Under-construction
Gujju, Thatta, Sindh	14 MW	1	Under-assessment
Jhimpir, Sindh	50 MW	2	Under-assessment
Jhimpir, Sindh	51 MW	1	Under-assessment

6.3 Micro-Hydro/Hydroelectric Power Projects in Pakistan

In Pakistan, out of 3000 MW Micro-Hydel, only 150 MW has been utilized. Not only these but there also are some small-micro hydropower projects, located in remote areas of northern Pakistan.

Recently, the government has identified the need for fuel technology and how to utilize indigenous resources to generate power. They have announced an Indicative Generation Capacity Expansion Plan (IGCEP). The plan envisages the projects of an additional 13,000 MW of hydropower till 2030 with an existing capacity of 9000 MW.

Pakistan has always seen ups and downs in maintaining renewable energies; however, it is almost cyclical. These projects came into existence after the friendly government energy policies and incentives.

- The Diamer-Bhasha Dam's construction will add 4,500MW of hydroelectric power; the dam is expected to be completed by 2028.
- The Mohmand Dam project, aiming to add 800MW of hydroelectric power, is scheduled to be completed by 2024.
- The installed capacity of Tarbela hydroelectric was increased from 1,410MW to 4,888MW. It is the fourth extension of the hydropower project. In the pipeline is the fifth extension, which will increase further capacity to 6,298MW.

- By April 2022, the total share of hydroelectric power was around 25% (10,251MW).

All these projects will enhance the country's potential for renewable energy and strengthen the country's economic backbone. Soon, if the progress continues, the country will be self-sufficient, and we won't be buying renewable energy to manage our energy distribution (9).

6.4 Other Renewable Energy Projects in Pakistan

Some of the other promising opportunities that can be leveraged to expand the energy sector of Pakistan are given below (9).

- **Biogas Energy:** In Pakistan, biogas is less preferred. In other words, the potential of biogas is taken for granted and underestimated. It is dubbed chiefly as "Gobar Gas," just useable for cooking. Only 1000 household plants have been installed compared to 932,000 in India and 43 million in China.
- **Tidal Energy:** Tidal power still needs to be explored in Pakistan compared to other renewable energies. In Sindh, we have a creek system of the Indus Delta with immense five meters of tidal height at Korangi Creek. Another potential spot is Sonmiani Beach and Kalamat in Balochistan with the prospect of tidal energy.

6.5 Upcoming IPP's

Here are the list of renewable energy upcoming IPP's in Pakistan (10).

Table 12: Alternative & Renewable Energy Upcoming IPPS

Upcoming IPPs Solar				
Sr. #	Name of Project	Capacity	Location	Expected COD/Remarks
1	Meridian Energy (Pvt.) Ltd	50 MW	Sukkur, Sindh	Nov, 2023
2	HND Energy (Pvt.) Limited	50 MW	Sukkur, Sindh	Nov, 2023
3	Helios Power (Pvt.) Limited	50 MW	Sukkur, Sindh	Nov, 2023
Upcoming IPPs Wind				
1	50 MW Western Energy (Private) Limited	50 MW	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fall under Cat-II • Generation License (G.L) acquired. IPP has filed for modification of G.L due to changes in technology. • Fresh tariff petition filed. • LOS to be issued after modification of G.L and determination of tariff by NEPRA.
2	50 MW Transatlantic Energy Private Limited	50 MW		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fall under Cat-II • Generation License (G.L) acquired. IPP has filed for modification of G.L due to changes in technology. • Fresh tariff petition filed. • LOS to be issued after modification of G.L and determination of tariff by NEPRA.
Upcoming IPP Biomass				
1	Shah Taj Sugar Mills Ltd.	32	Mandi Bahauddin	Jan, 2024
Total of Upcoming IPPs: 282 MW * CPEC Projects				

7 Organizations/Institutes Involved in Policy Making of Renewable Energy Resources in Pakistan

Following are the organizations that are involved in policy making of renewable energy resources in Pakistan.

7.1 Institutional Organization of Pakistan's Power Sector

According to the Policy for Development of Renewable Energy for Power Generation, 2006 (11) below is the Institutional Organization of Pakistan's Power Sector.

Figure 7: Institutional Organization of Pakistan's Power Sector

The landscape of renewable energy policy making in Pakistan has undergone a recent change. Following are the key organizations and institutes involved:

1. AEDB merges with PPIB:

In June 2023, the Alternative Energy Development Board (AEDB), previously the primary body for RE policy, merged with the Private Power & Infrastructure Board (PPIB). This created a single entity for facilitating all power projects, including renewables. Therefore, the PPIB now takes on the former responsibilities of the AEDB in policy formulation.

2. Ministry of Energy (Power Division):

Sets overall energy policy direction and oversees the PPIB.

3. National Electric Power Regulatory Authority (NEPRA):

Independent regulator responsible for licensing, setting tariffs, and monitoring the power sector, including renewables.

4. Provincial and AJK Agencies:

Play a role in developing and implementing renewable energy policies within their jurisdictions. This includes Irrigation and Power (I&P) Departments and specialized bodies like Sarhad Hydro Development Organization (SHYDO) in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

5. Pakistan Atomic Energy Commission (PAEC):

Responsible for development of nuclear power, which while not strictly renewable, is considered as a clean energy source within Pakistan's energy mix.

7.2 Other Relevant Organizations

1. Academia and Research Institutions:

Conduct research and provide technical expertise on renewable energy resources and technologies.

2. Civil Society Organizations (CSOs):

Advocate for and monitor the implementation of renewable energy policies.

3. International Organizations and Donors:

Provide funding and technical assistance for renewable energy projects and policy development.

7.3 Energy Policies Regarding Renewable Energy in Pakistan

A Comprehensive Timeline of Renewable Energy Policy in Pakistan (1947-2024).

7.3.1 Early Years (1947-1970s)

- **Limited focus on renewables:** Hydropower was the primary clean energy source, with major investments in Tarbela and Mangla dams.
- **Dominant reliance on fossil fuels:** Oil and gas exploration and infrastructure development gained traction due to perceived affordability and abundance.
- **Implicit recognition of renewables:** Initiatives like rural electrification and self-sufficiency programs hinted at the potential of renewables for remote areas.

7.3.2 Emerging Recognition (1970s-1990s)

- **1973 oil crisis:** Resource insecurity due to the crisis prompted exploration of alternatives.
- **1976:** Establishment of the Alternative Energy Development Board (AEDB) marked a pivotal shift towards dedicated development of renewable energy resources.
- **1994 Renewable Energy Policy:** First dedicated policy outlining the government's commitment to promoting renewable energy through:
 - **Financial incentives:** Grants, subsidies, and tax breaks for renewable energy projects.
 - **Research and development:** Support for research institutions and technology transfer.
 - **Awareness creation:** Public education campaigns and capacity building programs.

7.3.3 Sluggish Progress (1990s-2010s)

- **Limited implementation:** Despite policy revisions in 2002 and 2010, attracting significant investment and achieving major growth remained challenging.
- **Continued reliance on fossil fuels:** Existing infrastructure and perceived cost-effectiveness of fossil fuels overshadowed renewables.
- **Institutional and financial constraints:** Limited funding, bureaucratic hurdles, and inadequate market mechanisms hampered progress.

7.3.4 Renewed Drive (2010s-Present)

- **2013 Renewable Energy Policy**
- **Feed-in tariffs:** Guaranteed purchase price for renewable energy generated, making it more attractive for investors.
- **Streamlined approvals:** Simplified procedures for project development and licensing.
- **Net-metering:** Allowing consumers with small-scale renewable systems to export excess electricity to the grid.
- **Renewable Energy Fund:** Dedicated funding mechanism for research, development, and deployment of renewable technologies.
- **Increased focus:** Growing energy demand, environmental concerns, and depleting fossil fuel reserves pushed renewables back into the spotlight.
- **2030 Target:** Ambitious goal to generate 60% of electricity from renewables by 2030, necessitating further policy action and infrastructure development.

7.3.5 Recent Developments (2020s)

Merger of AEDB with the Private Power & Infrastructure Board (PPIB) aimed at:

- Streamlining project approvals and attracting more private investment.
- Creating a one-stop shop for all power project development, including renewables.

7.3.6 Ongoing Challenges

Grid integration, financing constraints, and transmission infrastructure limitations remain key areas for policy focus.

7.3.7 Other Initiatives and Programs

Several other initiatives and programs contributed to the evolution of renewable energy in Pakistan, such as:

1. National Renewable Energy Fund (NREF)
2. Hydel Power Development Programme (HPDP)
3. Small Hydropower Programme (SHP)
4. Independent Power Producers (IPPs) for Renewable Energy
5. International organizations and donors played a significant role in providing technical assistance and funding for renewable energy projects and policy development.

7.4 Key Policies and Strategies

Following are the key policies and strategies regarding renewable energy resources in Pakistan.

7.4.1 Development of Renewable Energy for Power Generation in Pakistan, 2006

The Renewable Energy Policy for Power Generation in Pakistan (11) outlines several strategies and policies to promote the development of renewable energy. Here are some key strategies and policies:

- 1. Gradual Transition to Competitive and Deregulated Market:**

The policy envisions a transition towards a more competitive and deregulated renewable energy market environment as experience, business confidence, and domestic industry capacity grows.
- 2. Integration with Social Infrastructure:**

The policy aims to optimize the impact of renewable energy deployment in underdeveloped areas by integrating energy solutions with the provision of other social infrastructure such as educational and medical facilities, clean water supply, sanitation, roads, and telecommunications to promote greater social welfare, productivity, trade, and economic well-being among deprived communities.
- 3. Capacity Building:**

The policy aims to help in broad institutional, technical, and operational capacity building relevant to the renewable energy sector.
- 4. Establishment of Domestic Manufacturing Base:**

The policy aims to facilitate the establishment of a domestic renewable energy technologies (RET) manufacturing base in the country to help lower costs, improve service, create employment, and enhance local technical skills.
- 5. Incentives for Private Sector Participation:**

The policy provides lenient policy measures and incentives in the short term to attract investment in renewable energy projects, remove existing barriers to project implementation, and support pioneering projects through to successful commercial operation.
- 6. Guaranteed Market and Production Incentives:**

The policy offers incentives such as guaranteed purchase of electricity, grid connection, off-take voltage, wheeling, production incentives, and security package to support grid-connected renewable energy independent power producers (IPPs)

7. Environmental Protection and Social Equity:

The policy aims to address issues related to social equity and environmental protection by promoting widespread renewable energy deployment, reducing the burden on rural communities, and circumventing the local environmental and health impacts of traditional biomass fuels and fossil fuel-powered electricity generation.

These strategies and policies demonstrate the government's commitment to promoting renewable energy development, attracting private sector investment, and addressing social, economic, and environmental challenges through the deployment of renewable energy technologies in Pakistan.

7.4.2 Sustainability in National Power Policy, 2013

The policy principle of sustainability in the National Power Policy 2013 (12) applies to the topic of power generation, transmission, and distribution in several ways.

- The policy aims to develop a sustainable and affordable power generation system that meets the needs of the population and boosts the economy in a sustainable manner.
- Secondly, the policy aims to alter the fuel mix towards less expensive fuels, which will lead to low-cost energy. This will require investments and rationalization of the electricity tariff, which will ensure the sustainability of the power sector.
- Thirdly, the policy aims to create a level playing field by providing power at comparable prices to all industrial users and protecting the poor by cross subsidizing their consumption from the affluent. This will ensure fairness and sustainability in the power sector.
- Lastly, the policy aims to introduce demand management through novel policy, pricing, and regulatory instruments. This will help to manage the demand for electricity and ensure the sustainability of the power sector.

Overall, the policy principle of sustainability is an essential component of the National Power Policy 2013, as it aims to ensure that the power sector is developed in a sustainable and affordable manner that meets the needs of the population and boosts the economy.

7.4.3 Alternative & Renewable Energy Policy, 2019

Policies regarding renewable energy are formulated to promote the development and utilization of renewable energy sources. These policies (13) typically aim to achieve various objectives such as environmental sustainability, energy security, and economic development. Some common policies related to renewable energy include:

1. Renewable Energy Targets:

Setting specific targets for the share of renewable energy in the overall energy mix, such as aiming for a certain percentage of energy generation from renewable sources by a particular year.

2. Feed-in Tariffs:

Establishing a pricing mechanism that guarantees a specific rate for electricity generated from renewable sources, providing financial incentives for renewable energy producers.

3. Renewable Energy Incentives:

Offering financial incentives, tax credits, or subsidies to encourage investment in renewable energy projects and technologies.

4. Renewable Portfolio Standards (RPS):

Requiring utilities to produce or procure a certain percentage of their electricity from renewable sources.

5. Net Metering:

Allowing individuals or businesses that generate their own renewable energy to feed excess electricity back into the grid and receive credit for it.

6. Renewable Energy Certificates (RECs):

Creating a market for tradable certificates that represent the environmental attributes of renewable energy generation, providing a way to incentivize renewable energy production.

These policies are designed to create a favorable environment for the growth of renewable energy and to address challenges related to climate change, energy security, and sustainable development.

8 Industries and Manufacturer of Renewable Energy Sources in Pakistan

Here are some key industries and manufacturers involved in renewable energy in Pakistan:

Table 13: Industries and manufacturers involved in renewable energy in Pakistan

Company	Category	Location
Dynamic Renewables (Pvt.) Ltd.	Solar Energy	8, Sika Street, Raiwind Road, Lahore
Reon Energy	Solar Energy	Islamabad, Capital Territory
United Energy Group Limited	Wind Energy	Sindh Province, Pakistan
Vestas Wind Systems	Wind Energy	Karachi, Sindh
Pakistan Solar Services	Solar Energy, Wind Energy, Biogas Energy	Office # 6, 2nd Floor, B.B. Shopping Mall, Opposite Ned University, Block-1, Gulistan-E-Johar, Karachi, Sindh
Multiline Engineering Company	Wind Energy, Solar Energy	3-A 1, Opposite Toyota Motors, Off Airport Road, Lahore.
Spiral Ways Pvt Limited	Wind Energy, Solar Energy, Biogas Energy	Apartment No. E-15, New Spinzer It Towers, University Road, Peshawar-Pakistan.
Truepower	Solar Energy, Wind Energy	P.E.C.H.S Block 6, Karachi, Sindh.
Nawal Khan Solar Energy Solutions	Solar Energy	Wazirabad Road, Rahimpur, Ugoke, Sialkot.
Sharp Energy (Pvt.) Ltd	Solar Energy, Wind Energy	34-1-C1, Butt Chowk, College Road, Township., Lahore, Punjab
Enabling Solutions (Smc-Pvt.) Ltd	Solar Energy	Office No. 4-A, 2nd Floor, Pakland City Center, I-8 Markaz, Islamabad Capital Territory
Rehman Hydro Engineering Taxila	Hydro Energy	Gangu Chok Near Uet Taxila Khapur Road, Taxila.
Solar Dynamics Technologies Corp.	Solar Energy	M-45-44-43,Zainab Towers. Link Road Model Town ,Lahore.
Solar Asia (Private) Limited	Solar Energy	Tf-116 Deans Trade Center Peshawar.
Automation Arena (Smc-Pvt.) Ltd.	Solar Energy	Office # 05 Ground Floor Humayun Arcade Street 14 Sector G-14/4, Islamabad.
Global Energy & Trading Company	Solar Energy	Pindi Bypass , Crescent Star Road, Gujranwala, Punjab.
Innosol Pakistan	Wind Energy, Solar Energy	4-D, 1st Floor, Mahmood Plaza, Fazal-UI-Haq Road, Blue Area, Islamabad Capital Territory
Hydropak International	Hydro Energy	Office 7, Icon I Plaza Commercial Area New City Phase II , Wah Cantonment, Punjab
Powerhub Enterprises	Solar Energy	Off # 10a, Ittehad Center, Main Fazal-E-Haq Rd, Blue Area, Islamabad Capital Territory
Chitral Engineering Works	Hydro Energy	Khanpur Road Near Uet Taxila, Taxila.
Revgreen	Biogas Energy	Galaxy Center , Muslim Town, Lahore.
Delux Energy	Solar Energy	Punjab, Rawalpindi
Solartech Power System	Solar Energy	House No. E-313, Block E, Satellite Town, Rawalpindi.
The Dawood Group	Solar Energy	11th Floor, Dawood Centre, M.T. Khan Road, Karachi.
Sky Green Engineering -Systems And Projects	Solar Energy	Quaid Plaza, Aziz Bhatti Road, Nowshera, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa
Solar Studio	Solar Energy	Punjab, Lahore
Sunvolts	Solar Energy	House 11 Street 22, Sector J Dha Phase II, Islamabad, Islamabad Capital Territory
Lakeside Energy	Wind Energy, Solar Energy	2p6j+Q8g, Unnamed Road, Thatta, Sindh, Karachi

9 Conclusions

In conclusion, Pakistan has made significant strides in the development of renewable energy resources, particularly in wind and solar energy. The country's geographical location and natural resources provide ample opportunities for the expansion of renewable energy projects. The government's commitment to renewable energy, as evidenced by policies and incentives, has also played a crucial role in attracting investment and promoting sustainable energy development.

However, there are still challenges that need to be addressed to fully realize the potential of renewable energy in Pakistan. These include issues related to grid integration, financing constraints, and transmission infrastructure limitations. Additionally, there is a need for greater coordination and collaboration among stakeholders, including government agencies, private sector companies, and international organizations, to ensure the effective implementation of renewable energy policies and projects.

Overall, the future of renewable energy in Pakistan looks promising, with ongoing projects and upcoming IPPs poised to further expand the country's renewable energy capacity. With continued support from the government and a concerted effort from all stakeholders, Pakistan can achieve its goal of generating 60% of its energy from renewable resources by 2030, contributing to a more sustainable and environmentally friendly energy sector.

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